

Reading Comprehension Strategies of Teachers: Amplifying Reading Literacy

Joash Gideon D. Reputana

Abstract. This study uncovered the reading comprehension strategies of teachers to amplify reading literacy. There were ten (10) elementary teachers from the intermediate level of San Isidro, North District, Division of Davao Oriental, who participated in the study. This study used a phenomenological approach to extract the participants' ideas. An in-depth interview gathered information regarding their reading strategies, coping mechanisms, and insights. Using the thematic analysis, the following themes emerged: making connections, questioning, predicting, and summarizing. Three themes were identified to overcome challenges in employing reading strategies: scaffolding, independent learning, and giving feedback. The insights drawn from the study's findings were teacher training, provision of resources and support, and flexibility in adapting methods. The importance of reading strategies was highly underscored in this study, which were fundamental skills that enable learners to develop their higher-order and critical thinking skills. Results also revealed that teachers and other sources of support were contributors to reading literacy. To make this study meaningful, publication in a reputable journal is essential.

KEY WORDS

1. reading strategies 2. scaffolding 3. making connections

Date Received: October 05, 2024 — Date Reviewed: November 10, 2024 — Date Published: December 10, 2024

1. Introduction

Comprehension strategies help readers build understanding, overcome difficulties in comprehending a text, and compensate for weak or imperfect knowledge related to the text. These strategies can be taught individually or in combination, as both approaches have been shown to improve reading comprehension. Moreover, teaching reading strategies is very important because it helps readers infer meaning, make conclusions, and generalize information. Reading strategies are beneficial for texts that have complex ideas and vocabulary. They can use them to develop comprehension skills and become better readers. Globally, Clarke et al. (2013); Wong (2011), and Ruiz (2015) posited that reading comprehension is a critical learning skill for all students, as it is “the process of simultaneously extracting and constructing meaning through interaction and involvement with written language” (Rand Reading Study Group, 2002). Understanding words' meaning, analyzing the author's points of view and aim for writing, and gaining knowledge of new words are all very important reading skills that support reading comprehension. Students need reading comprehension skills to successfully

accomplish the educational goals and expectations that are required in classroom settings. For example, having the ability to understand textual information plays a critical role in helping learners to locate information that is pertinent to the text quickly, exclude information that is irrelevant to the text, and identify the important information to focus on. Academic success also requires students to understand, analyze, and apply the information they gathered through their reading (Clarke et al., 2013). Understanding written materials increases significantly in all academic areas as students move from one grade to another (Clarke et al., 2013; Wong, 2011). Similarly, Gersten et al. (2001), Stetter Hughes (2010), and the US Department of Education (2003). Regarding students identified as having learning disabilities, approximately 80% of school. It is crucial to help students with reading difficulties overcome the reading problems that may prevent them from literacy success before they reach the fourth grade. This is because, in lower-level elementary grades, students are focused on learning to read, while students beyond third grade are reading to learn (Sloat et al., 2007; Clarke et al., 2013). Failing to solve reading difficulties during students' early grades dramatically increases the likelihood that the reading difficulties will follow them into their adult years (Ford Opitz, 2008; Samuelsson et al., 2004). Sloat, Beswick, and Willms (2007) stated that the majority of students who do not master the skills of reading by the end of third grade will never learn to read well, have more difficulties with the grade level curriculum, need ongoing intensive assistance, and perform less than their classmates in reading achievement and curricular knowledge. Thus, the critical role that reading plays in students learning beyond third grade emphasizes the importance of identifying struggling readers in their early grades and providing them with the

most appropriate reading strategies (Antoniou Souvignier, 2007; Sloat et al., 2007). In the Philippines, education is hindered by poverty, technology, and lack of motivation and inspiration, especially reading education. Despite their socioeconomic status, many Filipinos are unable to learn. Some families do not have enough money to send their kids to school; thus, kids grow up unable to read and write. Some families are marginally fortunate that they can send their children to a public school; however, their children are learning essential reading at a plodding pace as there are not enough teachers and up-to-date reading materials in this school. The Philippines had the highest rate of low performers among all PISA-participating countries and economies. That is, 80% of Filipino students did not reach the minimum level of proficiency in reading. Their poor scores in English, Mathematics, and Science are attributed to their lack of ability in basic reading and comprehension. Research has shown that there are many reasons for the difference in the achievement level of students. Luz (2007) stresses that many Filipino learners do not have the reading habits required for learning. She noted, "The problem of non-reading lies at the heart of why the Philippines is so uncompetitive in the world economy and why so many of our people continue to live in poverty or barely escape it." In the local, the Department of Education (DepEd) has launched the Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa (3Bs Initiatives) to intensify reading advocacy and pledge to make every learner a reader at his/her grade level. Such reasons prompted the researcher to conduct a study on the reading comprehension strategies of teachers in San Roque Elementary, San Isidro North District, Division of Davao Oriental. In particular, exploring the teachers' reading comprehension strategies to cater to individual reading needs and be able to amplify reading literacy in school.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study aimed to explore the reading comprehension strategies of elementary teachers to amplify reading literacy in school. This presents an opportunity for teachers to improve the teaching-learning process through the application of reading comprehension strategies. This study would also dig into the issues or challenges, as well as the coping strategies of teachers, in order to generate educational management insights that was helpful in addressing the poor comprehension skills of learners.

1.2. Research Questions—The primary research questions of this study were the following:

- (1) What are the reading comprehension strategies of teachers to amplify reading literacy?
- (2) How do they cope with the challenges while employing the reading comprehension strategies?
- (3) What educational management insights are drawn from the strategies of teachers?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms were defined for use in this study: Reading comprehension. Reading comprehension is a complex cognitive process involving various skills and strategies crucial for academic success and everyday life. Reading comprehension strategies are techniques and approaches that readers use to understand and interpret text more effectively. These strategies help readers engage with the material, make sense of it, and

retain important information. Reading literacy. Reading literacy refers to reading, understanding, interpreting, and critically engaging with written texts. It encompasses a range of skills and competencies related to reading comprehension and fluency. Reading literacy involves the mechanical skill of decoding written words (reading the words on a page) and the capacity to comprehend and analyze the content, extract information, make inferences, and evaluate the text's reliability and relevance.

1.4. Significant of the Study—The findings reported in this study would have important implications for educational authorities and professional practice. Specifically for the following individuals: Policy Makers. The findings of the study would give them ideas to make a curriculum in which reading comprehension strategies would be easily adapted. They may also empower themselves to make well-informed decisions, communicate effectively, and navigate the complex and ever-changing landscape of policy development. These skills ultimately contribute to the creation of more effective and responsive policies that benefit society as a whole particularly in the promotion of reading literacy. School Administrators. The findings of the study would give them ideas on what skills, knowledge and resources are needed for teachers to effectively improve learners reading

comprehension skills. They may prioritize the promotion of these strategies to ensure that all students have the opportunity to excel academically and become capable, informed, and critical thinkers. School heads as providers of instructional and technical support to contextualize and improve school-based reading programs aligned with the national standards to promote school reading programs, improve pedagogical practices, and enhance teachers' efficacy in teaching reading through capacity-building; Teachers. Educational management insights formulated in this study could guide them in improving their delivery of reading comprehension teaching strategies. Teachers could benchmark best practices from the experiences of the participants and could analyze and reflect effectively the challenges they encounter in the delivery of the intervention, thus uplifting their passion

and motivation in teaching. Teachers as reading teachers are classroom managers and facilitators of learning; the result of this study may give a better understanding of their roles and functions in promoting literacy and encourage them to perform effectively in the implementation of reading programs; Parents. The results of this study may be utilized to offer workshops, resources, and guidance on how parents can integrate these strategies into their interactions with their children. Additionally, demonstrating the benefits through improved academic performance and enriched family experiences can motivate parents to prioritize these skills in their children's development. Students. This study would be

significant to them as they may greatly benefit from the application of appropriate reading comprehension strategies and the promotion of reading interventions, programs, and activities appropriate to their reading needs; Stakeholders. This study would be significant to them since it would give them ideas on how to assist the school in strengthening reading programs. They would also be able to assist the school principal and teachers in making action plans and school improvement plans related to reading. Future Researchers. The findings provided comprehensive data for future research with similar or relevant scope.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study is anchored on theories of reading comprehension that have emerged over the years. These include the bottom-up view, the top-down view, and the interactive view of reading comprehension. These three views are connected to the Development Delay theory of students' reading comprehension skills due to the challenges and issues present in the delivery of reading instruction. According to the bottom-up view of reading comprehension by Gough (1972), readers move from an understanding of parts of the language (e.g., letters, words) to an understanding of the meaning or the whole (e.g., phrases, passages). Comprehension is thought to be a product of the acquisition of hierarchically arranged subskills (Dole et al., 1991). Thus, lower-level word recognition skills precede the development of more complex skills that lead to an eventual understanding of phrases, sentences, and paragraphs. Automaticity in processing and understanding written text is also thought to affect text comprehension (LaBerge Samuels, 1974). Automaticity refers to the fact that proficient readers can read text automatically and that they do not need to focus consciously on lower-level word recognition. Thus,

children with decoding problems allot greater cognitive resources to word recognition – and less to comprehension – whereas proficient readers are able to devote greater cognitive resources to higher-level cognitive processes (Daneman Carpenter, 1980). Based on the top-down (i.e., conceptually-driven) view of reading comprehension (Rumelhart, 1980), readers are moving from meaning down to the component parts of words as they engage with the text. According to this view, a reader's mental frameworks or schemas are the driving force behind successful reading comprehension (Rumelhart, 1980). Readers are actively integrating new information that is encountered in the text with information that they have already stored within their previously established mental representations (i.e., background knowledge). Further, top-down and bottom-up aspects are combined in the interactive view of reading comprehension. Based on this view, explained by Perfetti et al., (2005), reading comprehension requires the reader to devote attentional resources to the more basic features of the text (e.g., letters, words) while simultaneously focusing on the more general aspects (e.g., syntax, semantics) and actively interpreting what is being read (Per-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

fetti et al., 2005). Proficient readers are those who successfully engage with multiple sources of information provided within the text and information that is not readily available from the text (Kintsch, 1998). Good readers can recognize and interact with key features of the text, such as lexical characteristics, at the same time that they are more broadly identifying the purpose of a passage or a paragraph (Rayner, 1986) Moreover, developmental delay is often discussed about the nature of reading problems. The Developmental Delay Theory of Francis et al. (1996) asserts that poor reading performance results from a delayed acquisition of reading-related skills. However, these children follow the same developmental trajectory as typical readers (Francis et al., 1996). For example, in the case of reading difficulty, the underlying skill Francis et al. (1996) examined was phonological processing. The authors of the theory

found that an oral language weakness represents a developmental delay for children. This was tested within studies regarding the comprehension age of typically developing children. Francis et al. (1996) noted that providing children with strong literacy education in the early years leads to better outcomes. Between the ages of zero and three, the brain develops faster than at any other time. Because of this, it is essential to foster literacy during the early stages of life. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. Based on the figure, there are two interconnected variables. These variables are the (1) reading comprehension strategies of teachers to amplify reading literacy, (2) coping mechanisms of teachers while employing reading comprehension strategies, and (3) educational management insights drawn from the strategies of teachers.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research design used, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection and analysis, the trustworthiness, and the ethical considerations. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) is optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when exploring sensitive topics. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks the question, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" "the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the reading comprehension strategies of teachers to amply reading literacy. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation greater in depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research – undertaking with the selection of the topic, problem or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces 'paradigm back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm) meaning pattern, model or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions were taken. Differently stated, a paradigm is an action of submitting to a view. This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who defend a research paradigm as a "basic set of beliefs that guide action," dealing with first principles, "ultimates' or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains on how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012) reality is a subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher.

Reality is constructed by individuals involved in the research situation, thus, multiple realists exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the participants discussed realities regarding teachers' strategies and tried to examine their ways of coping with challenges. In this study, I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant's answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study in order to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln (1985), as cited by Creswell (2013), state that on epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen

distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an “insider.” Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). I identified phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers “hold explicit belief”. The intention of this study is to gather information from the participants or the teachers who employed reading comprehension strategies following the guidelines set by DepEd and the Inter Agency Task Force (IATF). I assured to establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that shed light to the knowledge behind the inquiry particularly on the experiences and the challenges of teachers employing reading comprehension strategies. Axiology refers to role of values in research. Creswell (2013) avers that the role

of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their own interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. I upheld the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understood the personal and the value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. I, therefore, preserved the merit of the participant’s answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participant’s personal interpretation. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using a personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions. In the study, the researcher used the first person to elucidate the teachers’ experiences as they employed reading comprehension strategies in class.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology is different from the method. Methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the reading comprehension strategies of teachers were gathered through an in-depth interview (IDI), and the challenges and coping mechanisms encountered by the participants were extracted. The researcher’s inquisitiveness on the strategies of teachers as they employed reading comprehension strategies became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means by which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013), considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences and phenomena”. By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and

meaning of the experiences will be presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first is that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs (2006), experience was a source of knowledge that shapes one’s behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge. We can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology, which concerns the “what” and the “how” (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher hoped that the subjective experiences and perspectives of the participants, who happened to be teachers, would provide highlights as to how these reading comprehen-

sion strategies amplify reading literacy. Design and Procedure

This study used qualitative research employing phenomenology. Interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994). The data was then read and reread, and culled for phrases and themes that were then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this process, the

researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. In this study, phenomenology attempted to extract the most pure, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher used bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is memoing (Maxwell, 2013).

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—

2.4. *Research Participants*—This study involved ten (10) informants. The selected informants were elementary teachers from the Intermediate Level of San Isidro North District, male or female, who had been in the service for at least three years and above. Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions will lead to saturation. Saturation occurs when more participants are added

to the study, which does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25, and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There are no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990).

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations were of paramount importance in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues about the research participant groups addressed in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most critical parts of the research. The researcher must also adhere to promoting the aims of the research, imparting factual knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value. In this study, I focus on social value by exploring the experiences of teachers who implement reading comprehension strategies. The social issue that interested me was the

challenges these teachers encounter while using these strategies. This research could provide a foundation for higher authorities to develop programs and solutions to benefit the school and its stakeholders. Informed Consent. In this consent form, I outlined specific details about the study, including my purpose, the nature of the research, and how their contributions would be utilized. I had to include clear contact information so that participants could reach out with any questions or concerns. The letter articulated my intent to invite them to participate in the study, emphasizing that their involvement was optional. Additionally, I specified the information I expected them to provide, ensuring that participants felt

informed about the process. I proceeded with the interviews only after the participants signed and returned the consent form, ensuring that I had their explicit agreement to participate in the research journey. This approach not only underscored the ethical considerations of the study but also fostered an atmosphere of trust and respect with the participants. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation as cited by McLeod (2009) was adhered to. The invitation to participate ensured that participation in the research was entirely voluntary in nature, and based on an understanding of adequate information. The participant recruitment and selection were lodged in the appendices of this study. The Vulnerability of Research Participants. As the researcher, I determined that the participants of this study were well-equipped to answer the research instrument, as they were all professional teachers. I assured them they could easily be contacted through their phone numbers and addresses if any clarifications or questions about the study arose. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. As a researcher, I ensured respondents were recruited without coercion, undue influence, or inducement. I provided respondents with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members so they could reach out with any questions related to the study. This was intended to address any potential inquiries they might have. Additionally, if any respondents felt discomfort or inconvenience while answering the questions, I made it clear that they were not compelled to participate in any way. I prioritized the safety of the respondents throughout the survey and interview process. Therefore, I distributed the questionnaire in a safe environment and scheduled it for a convenient time. My primary focus in this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, which included respecting the rights to privacy and confidentiality while minimizing risk. To protect their identities, I assigned pseudonyms to each informant. I took all reasonable steps

to ensure participant confidentiality and minimize potential risks. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. In this study, I adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data could not be traced back to its original sources, thereby protecting the participants' identities. I took great care to maintain the anonymity of the data sources, and any printed outputs from the study were also kept anonymous. I considered all potential issues to avoid any conflicts of interest between the respondents and me. Additionally, I prioritized avoiding any misleading information and biased representation of the primary data findings. Justice. I informed the respondents about my role as the researcher and their role during the data-gathering process. I emphasized the importance of providing honest answers to the survey questions and communicating transparently about the research. I also told them they would be the first to benefit from the study's results. Transparency. As a researcher, I made sure that the results of my study would be accessible to the respondents and the heads of the participating schools by placing the information on CDs and other storage devices, which they could request from me. By reviewing the study's findings, I hope that classroom teachers will understand the significance of my research and how it contributes to their well-being. I informed each participant that they have the right to withdraw their information before the data collection was completed, and they can request to verify their transcript after the interview. I also allowed them to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. To protect the identities of my participants, I reserve the right to use pseudonyms and change names or non-significant dates during all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. As a researcher, I ensured the necessary qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher had completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination before thesis writing,

which is the last requirement to obtain the researcher's master's degree. They are qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. Also, the advisee-adviser tandem ensures that the study will be completed. Adequacy of Facilities. I strived to complete the study successfully within the specified time, equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee would enhance my paper by providing valuable suggestions and recommendations. I also needed to ensure I had enough funds to continue and finish my research. Community Involvement. I respected the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in my study. I ensured that no deceit would be used at any stage of the implemen-

tation, particularly in recruiting participants or collecting data. Moreover, I want to express my sincere gratitude for their participation in this research. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. I have made it a priority to respect the work of other researchers by accurately citing their contributions and expressing their ideas in my own words. I carefully considered the context of the study to avoid copying text verbatim from reference papers. When I included direct quotes, I ensured they were clearly marked as sourced from others. Furthermore, I have committed to upholding integrity in my manuscript, confirming that there was no intent to misrepresent the study, create false data or results, or present conclusions that do not reflect the truth.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The role of the researcher in this study was to attempt to access the thoughts and feelings of study participants. It involves asking informants to talk about things that may be very personal to them. Sometimes, the explored experiences are fresh in the participant's mind, whereas on other occa-

sions, reliving past experiences may be difficult. However the data are being collected, a primary responsibility of the researcher is to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and must be approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins.

2.7. Data Collection—According to Creswell (2013), an important step in the process is to find people or places to study and to gain access to and establish rapport with participants so that they will provide good data. A closely interrelated step in the process involves determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once the inquirer selects the sites or people, decisions must be made about the most appropriate data collection approaches. To collect this information, the researcher developed protocols or written forms for recording the data, such as interviews or observational protocols. Also, the researcher needed to anticipate issues of data collection, called "field issues," which may

be a problem, such as having inadequate data, needing to leave the field or site prematurely, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must decide how he or she will store data so that they can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. In this study, there were seven steps in the data collection process. First was the site or individual; the participants were the selected teachers of Magallanes Elementary School. Second was the access and rapport; a letter from the Dean of the Graduate School was given to the graduate student for the approval of the division superintendent; a letter of permission for the Schools Division Superintendent, the school Principal, and the concerned elementary teach-

ers was prepared for easy collection of data. The third was the purposeful sampling strategy; all participants experienced the phenomenon being studied. Ten (10) informants were selected for this study. The selected parents were considered individuals who can best inform the researcher about the research problem. They were also considered individuals who had experienced the phenomenon and could facilitate the collection of data. The fourth was the forms of data; the process of collecting information involved primarily in the In-Depth Interview

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with full description of her own experience of the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher’s personal experiences so that the focus can be directed to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. She then finds statements about how the individual was experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of non-repetitive, non-overlapping statements. The researcher

2.9. Framework of Analysis—Braun and Clark (2006) state that qualitative data analysis methods fall into two groups. The first group consists of methods driven by an epistemological or theoretical position, which have limited variability in how they are applied within their frameworks, such as conversation analysis (CA) and interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) and methods that are situated within a broad theoretical framework and can therefore be used in a variety of ways within those frameworks, such as grounded theory (GT), discourse analysis (DA) narrative analysis (NA). The sec-

(IDI) with the ten (10) informants. The fifth was the recording procedures; a protocol was used in the observation and interviewing procedures. A predesigned form records information collected during an observation or interview. The sixth was the field issues; limited data collection was engaged in this study. The last was the storing of data; Davidson (1996) suggested the use of the database to back up information collected and note changes for all types of research studies.

took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger units of information, called “meaning units” or themes. She wrote a description of “what” the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, he wrote a description of “how” the experience happened. This is called “structural description,” the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, she wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating textural and structural descriptions. This passage was the “essence” of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study.

ond group includes methods independent of theory and epistemology, which can be applied across a range of different theoretical and epistemological approaches and are therefore very flexible. One such method is thematic analysis, which, through theoretical freedom, “provides flexible and useful research tool, which can potentially provide a rich and detailed, yet complex account of data (Braun Clark, 2006). I observed several steps in conducting thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater

familiarity with the data and deeper insight. I relied on my own resources to do the transcription, using my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I spent several nights listening to the interviews to deepen my understanding of the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated themselves to lay-out and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved, and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step as data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note-taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included some process of verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues, or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used a number of different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. I used forms of thematic grids and charts, the framework technique as developed by the National Centre for Social Research (Ritchie et al., 2003). This technique was useful to me in the process of coding, sorting, and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was very useful in understanding links

and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedures included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross-referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) which consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. Phase 1. I familiarized myself with the data by reading the whole data set and noting down initial ideas; Phase 2. I generated initial codes, with code being the most basic segments of the raw data that can identify a feature of the data that appears interesting; Phase 3. I searched for themes by sorting different codes into potential themes and collated all data extracts within identified themes; Phase 4. I reviewed the themes and refined them further (at the level of coded data extracts and the entire data set) and produced a thematic map showing relationships between themes and sub themes; Phase 5. I defined and named themes, making sure they give the reader immediate sense of what the theme is all about. Phase 6. I wrote the report to convince the reader of the merit and validity of the analysis (within and across the themes) and used data extracts embedded within an analytic narrative to make arguments in relation to the research question. Figure 2 shows the steps in the process of the study's analytical framework, which involves familiarization, coding, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In qualitative studies, trustworthiness is vital because the research study's results and findings depend on the researcher's research process. The trustworthiness of a research study was important in evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of qualitative studies, honesty in all the data and details was required. Trustwor-

thiness makes the researcher's study worthy of reading, sharing, and being proud of. Credibility refers to how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study's findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do is essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues that ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) state that credibility refers to the idea

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

of internal consistency, where the main issue was “how we ensure rigor in the research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so.” Transferability was how the qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study’s findings apply to other contexts. In this case, “other contexts” can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader can generalize the study based on his context and address the core issue of “how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory.” Confirmability is the degree of neutrality in the research study’s findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants’ responses and not any potential bias or personal motivations of the researcher. This involves making sure that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the

decisions made. This helps establish that the research study’s findings accurately portray participants’ responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability is based on the acknowledgment that research is never objective. Dependability was the extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher can use an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings are consistent and can be repeated. In this component, the use of the database is very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected must be properly kept for future use as references. Gasson (2004) states that dependability deals with the core issue that “the way in which a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques.

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the results of the study are presented and discussed with reference to the aim of the study. The themes that emerged from the data gathered are discussed in this chapter. The results present the description and background of the participants who are assigned to pseudonyms to conceal their identity.

3.1. Reading Comprehension Strategies Of Teachers—Reading comprehension is a fundamental skill that serves as the cornerstone of academic achievement and lifelong learning. In today’s rapidly evolving society, where information is abundant and diverse, the ability to comprehend and critically analyze written texts is more crucial than ever. As such, educators play a pivotal role in fostering reading lit-

eracy among students, equipping them with the necessary tools to navigate complex texts, extract meaning, and engage with ideas effectively. This study explored the reading comprehension strategies employed by teachers to enhance reading literacy in their classrooms. Understanding the approaches educators use to teach reading comprehension can offer valuable insights into effective pedagogical methods and inform strategies for improving student outcomes.

3.1.1. Making Connections—

Making connections is a reading comprehension strategy that helps students find meaning in a text by connecting it to their background knowledge. It is particularly important for English language learners who need to connect learning to their experiences, culture, and family at home, and often across languages. Reading becomes more beneficial when you relate new and old information. You learn better when you connect new concepts to what you already know and apply your existing skills in various situations (Louse et al., 2020). By using this process, the students can read and understand better, as

3.1.2. Questioning—Questioning in reading is a reading comprehension strategy that involves using clues from the text and your background knowledge to figure out what the text means or what will happen next. When we ask questions in reading, we can enjoy many advantages. We can better understand texts and learn more from them (Mi-ea Gye, 2023). We can also start investigations, guide our thoughts, and make students think differently about information (Xu, 2023). Questioning also creates conversations, leads to new discoveries, and

3.1.3. Predicting—Predicting in reading is a reading comprehension strategy that involves using information from the text and your background knowledge to anticipate what will happen next or what the text will be about. When we make predictions in reading, we can enjoy many advantages. Predictions help us understand texts better by figuring out what they mean (Benedetta et al., 2022). They also help us read faster by directing our eyes to the important parts of the text (Mary et al., 2020). Moreover, making reasonable predictions helps us to grasp and expect how things will happen in a text (Vukile, 2021). In the field of technology-based education, predicting how students will do based on how they read can help us to create customized suggestions and help for them

shown by their improved comprehension scores from medium to very high (Fernando, 2018). When readers make connections, they can better understand what they read at six levels: word meaning, implied meaning, personal response, analysis, judgment, and evaluation (Judy et al., 2014). It also helps the readers to master more advanced comprehension skills, which are essential for doing well in school (Jo Jessica, 2013). By linking what they read and write, the readers can do better in both skills because reading and writing share similar processes (Kevin et al., 2009).

helps us dig deeper into facts and ideas (Melissa Michele, 2021). Moreover, questioning can help us improve our critical thinking skills and think at a higher level (Dung Trang, 2022). It helps us to think logically about real-world problems and change reality through practical activities (Douglas Nancy, 2018). Questioning in reading also helps us to enhance the quality of our thinking and develop our thinking skills. In summary, good questioning by teachers and students can make a big difference in how we learn and understand texts.

(Effat et al., 2022). In conclusion, predicting in reading improves understanding, makes reading easier, and enables personalized learning.

3.1.4. Summarizing —Summarizing is a reading skill that involves describing the most essential parts of a text in your own words in a shorter way. It helps readers understand the text's main ideas, ignore irrelevant information, and integrate the central ideas meaningfully. The ability to summarize is a cornerstone of effective reading comprehension in literacy and comprehension. Summarizing is not merely a task of condensing text; it is a strategic skill that empowers readers to distill key information, extract main ideas, and grasp the overarching meaning of a text. As such, summarizing serves as a powerful reading strategy that en-

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes On The Reading Comprehension Strategies Of Teachers

hances comprehension, promotes critical thinking, and fosters deeper engagement with written material. Reading summaries have many advantages. They help readers get the essential information from the text without losing its central theme (Vidyagouri BibiSadiqa, 2022). Summaries help readers comprehend the text better Highlighting the critical information and ideas (Maria Jahaira, 2021). Summaries also save reading time and make it simpler to find helpful knowledge (Abhishek et al., 2022). Moreover, using summaries in reading comprehension can improve students’ reading skills (Nguyen Nhu, 2021). Teachers can use summaries to teach writing topics, which can help students in both writing and reading. Figure 4 shows the emerging themes in teachers’ reading comprehension strategies. The emerging themes included making connections, questioning, independent learning, predicting, and summarizing.

3.2. *Coping mechanisms with the challenges of employing reading comprehension strategies*—Navigating through written text is a fundamental skill necessary for success in both academic and professional realms. However, comprehending written material can present various challenges, especially when dealing with complex or unfamiliar content. Effective

reading comprehension strategies are essential for overcoming these obstacles and extracting meaning from texts. They are exploring coping mechanisms designed to address the challenges of employing reading comprehension strategies. By understanding these coping mechanisms, individuals can enhance their ability to comprehend and analyze diverse texts, ultimately improving their reading proficiency.

3.2.1. *Scaffolding*—Scaffolding in reading is a technique that helps students to improve

their reading comprehension by providing them with support and guidance before, during, and

after reading a text. Scaffolding can include various strategies, such as previewing the text, asking questions, using visual aids, and reviewing the main ideas. Scaffolding helps students access more challenging texts and develop their independent reading skills. By using scaffolding instruction in reading, students can benefit in many ways. They can enjoy a more dynamic and supportive learning experience, which helps them to develop their reading abilities (Amaglobeli, 2023). Scaffolding from teachers is cru-

cial for the success of extensive reading (ER) programs (Xiaomei, 2022). Scaffolding techniques help students better comprehend texts, such as identifying themes, details, pronouns, and word meanings (Luh, 2022). Scaffolding strategies also assist students in improving their reading sub-skills and understanding readings with the teacher as a guide (Andres Janine, 2022). Scaffolding instruction in English reading increases students' motivation and reading proficiency (Yang, 2021).cols

3.2.2. Independent learning—Independent learning in reading is a practice that allows students to read texts of their own choice and interest with little or no help from adults. It helps students improve their reading skills, such as fluency, vocabulary, comprehension, and spelling. It also helps students develop their thinking skills, such as critical, logical, and creative thinking and problem-solving abilities. Independent learning in reading also fosters students' motivation, engagement, autonomy, and self-direction in reading. By reading independently, students can benefit in many ways. They can improve their thinking skills, such as being critical, logical, and creative, and also solve problems better (Isabella Aisyah, 2023). They can also be more involved in Reading and learn more effectively, especially when they read stories (Enny Zulkarain, 2022). Moreover, they can have more control and independence in reading and choose the books they like and enjoy (Sara Ramlee, 2017). This makes them more motivated and interested in reading and also lets them explore different types of literature and language (Ida Anik, 2013). Therefore, independent reading helps students learn, think

better, and love reading.

3.2.3. Giving feedback—Feedback in reading is the process of giving comments or suggestions to someone reading a text to help them improve their reading skills and comprehension. Feedback can come from different sources, such as teachers, peers, parents, or self-assessment. It can also focus on different aspects of reading, such as accuracy, fluency, vocabulary, strategies, or comprehension. Reading feedback is beneficial in many ways. It boosts learners' motivation and helps them use language correctly (Ramadani et al., 2022). Feedback that focuses on understanding the text enhances learning from the text and helps students use reading strategies better and more frequently, resulting in better reading comprehension (Elise et al., 2022). Children can improve their reading skills with supervised, supportive feedback while reading aloud (Yu et al., 2022). Furthermore, feedback can improve student performance in the classroom (Kristen Sara, 2020). Figure 4 shows the emerging themes in coping mechanisms for employing reading comprehension strategies. The emerging themes were scaffolding, learning language through immersion, independent learning, and giving feedback.

3.3. Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Strategies of Teachers—Acquir-

ing proficient reading skills is a cornerstone for academic success and lifelong learning. How-

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes On The Coping Mechanisms With The Challenges On Employing Reading Comprehension Strategies

ever, mastering reading comprehension is not solely about decoding words; instead, it involves a multifaceted process that requires learners to employ many strategies to extract meaning, infer context, and critically analyze text. This section delves into the educational insights drawn from the deliberate employment of reading comprehension strategies. By examining the efficacy of various approaches, exploring the impact on student outcomes, and highlighting the transformative potential for educators and learners, this discourse aimed to underscore the pivotal role of strategic comprehension in foster-

ing literacy proficiency and intellectual growth. Throughout this exploration, it is unraveling how strategic reading encompasses a spectrum of techniques, including activating prior knowledge, making predictions, visualizing, questioning, summarizing, and synthesizing information. These strategies enhance comprehension and empower individuals to engage deeply with diverse texts, fostering a deeper understanding of content across disciplines and uncovering the empirical insights that substantiate the value of strategic reading in educational contexts.

3.3.1. *Training for teachers*—Training for teachers in reading is a process of enhancing teachers’ knowledge, skills, and pedagogy in teaching reading to their students. It can involve various strategies and methods, such as reading aloud, phonics, word analysis, guided reading, partner reading, reading clinics, individualized reading instruction, literacy centers, and tutoring. Training for teachers in reading can help them improve their reading ability, ad-

dress their gaps in subject knowledge, adopt evidence and research-based instruction, and track and assess their students’ reading progress. Training for teachers in reading can also benefit their students, leading to better reading achievement, academic performance, and school outcomes. When teachers receive reading training, they benefit in many ways. For example, they improve their knowledge, skills, pedagogy, and confidence, which results in better read-

ing achievement for their students (Jane, 2021). They also overcome their gaps in subject knowledge, especially in phonics, which is essential for teaching young learners how to read (Naomi et al., 2021). Moreover, they develop their reading ability according to the PISA standards and learn how to produce and use suitable reading materials for their students (Emi et al., 2022). Furthermore, they adopt evidence and research-based instruction methods that help struggling

readers in disadvantaged communities (Celia et al., 2019). In summary, teacher training in reading is important for enhancing children's academic and school performance, promoting uniform and effective phonics instruction, improving teachers' assessment skills, and enabling teachers to make lasting and positive changes to their reading instruction practices (Katharine Andrew, 2023).

3.3.2. Provision of Resources and Support—Providing resources and support in reading refers to how educators, schools, and other stakeholders can help students who struggle with reading or have reading disabilities. There are many advantages of providing resources and support for reading. Well-designed Computer or app programs can make high-quality instruction more accessible and feasible, save time and resources for training experts, and save instructional time (Emily et al., 2023). Better

outcomes can result from continuous support for computer or app programs teaching reading (Ryan et al., 2019). Children who start with low reading scores can improve their academic performance and help their classmates with higher scores by getting educational support (Li Li, 2013). Struggling learners need support and guidance from teachers and in terms of learning resources. Families can help their children learn better at home by getting guidance, directives, materials, and support for reading (Samuel et al., 2022).

3.3.3. Flexibility in Adapting Methods—Flexibility in adapting methods in reading means adjusting and modifying the way you read according to the text's purpose, difficulty, and interest. It involves choosing the most appropriate reading strategy for different texts and situations. For example, you may use skimming, scanning, or summarizing to get the main idea of a text, or you may use close reading, annotating, or questioning to analyze a text in depth. Flexibility also means switching between dif-

ferent reading strategies as needed, depending on your goal and the text's features. Flexibility in reading methods can help language learners understand better (Shuqiang et al., 2012), it can help children with communication problems join in reading activities (Juliana et al., 2018). Figure 5 shows the three themes that speak about educational management Insights drawn from teachers' strategies, namely training for teachers, provision of resources and support, and flexibility in adapting methods.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents the study's summary. I drew the implications and future directions from the summary of the findings. My study aimed to discover the reading comprehension strategies, coping mechanisms, and insights from the study's findings as teachers amplify reading literacy. I used a qualitative phenomenological method with thematic analysis to achieve the research objectives. In adherence to Cresswell's (2006) guidelines, I used open-ended questions for

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes On The Insights Drawn From The Strategies Of Teachers interviews to get an authentic understanding of people’s experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored. These were teachers’ experiences in employing reading comprehension strategies.

Findings

Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the study participants, the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: the reading comprehension strategies delved into making connections, questioning, predicting, and summarizing. The

coping mechanisms employed were scaffolding, independent learning, and giving feedback. The insights drawn from the study’s findings were teacher training, provision of resources and support, and flexibility in adapting methods.

4.1. *Implications*—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. Teachers employed reading comprehension strategies to enhance reading literacy in their classrooms. Understanding the approaches educators use to teach reading comprehension can offer valuable insights into effective pedagogical methods and inform strategies for improving student outcomes. Effective reading comprehension strategies are essential for overcoming reading obstacles and extracting meaning from texts. In essence, reading comprehension strategies are not just about understanding

the words on the page; they are about equipping readers with the skills and mindset necessary to engage meaningfully with written text, both now and in the future. The coping mechanisms were designed to address the challenges of employing reading comprehension strategies. By understanding these coping mechanisms, individuals can enhance their ability to comprehend and analyze diverse texts, ultimately improving their reading proficiency. Further, coping mechanisms were essential for facilitating the effective application of reading comprehension strategies by helping readers manage challenges,

reduce stress, maintain focus, build resilience, enhance self-efficacy, promote metacognition, support different learning styles, and foster persistence. The pivotal role of strategic comprehension in fostering literacy proficiency and intellectual growth was underscored by examining the efficacy of various approaches, exploring the impact on student outcomes, and highlighting the transformative potential for both educators and learners. This exploration unravels how

strategic reading encompasses a spectrum of techniques, including activating prior knowledge, making predictions, visualizing, questioning, summarizing, and synthesizing information. These strategies enhance comprehension and empower individuals to engage deeply with diverse texts, fostering a deeper understanding of content across disciplines and uncovering the empirical insights that substantiate the value of strategic reading in educational contexts.

4.2. Future Directions—Based on the study’s findings, it was vital that they were properly relayed and used by the significant people for whom this research was intended. Curriculum Developers. Curriculum developers were key in designing educational materials and resources that align with learning objectives and standards. By integrating reading comprehension strategies into curriculum frameworks, textbooks, and digital learning platforms, developers can provide teachers and students with the tools to engage with diverse texts and develop advanced literacy skills effectively. Educational Administrators. Educational administrators are responsible for shaping curriculum standards, implementing instructional practices, and assessing student achievement. By promoting the use of research-based reading comprehension strategies across schools and districts, administrators can enhance literacy outcomes for all students, reduce achievement gaps, and improve overall academic performance. Teachers. Reading comprehension strategies were essential tools for supporting their students’ learning. Teachers can use these strategies to design effective lesson plans, select appropriate reading materials, and provide targeted instruction to address students’ diverse needs and abilities. By teaching comprehension strategies explicitly, teachers empower students to become more

proficient readers and achieve academic success. Parents. Parents play a vital role in fostering their children’s reading comprehension skills from an early age. By reading with their children, asking questions about the text, and modeling effective comprehension strategies, parents can help strengthen their children’s literacy development and support their academic progress. Additionally, parents can collaborate with teachers to reinforce comprehension strategies at home and monitor their children’s reading comprehension progress over time. Learners. For learners, reading comprehension strategies are crucial for academic success across all subjects. These strategies help students understand and analyze complex texts, improve retention of information, and develop critical thinking skills. Mastering comprehension strategies allows students to become more independent learners, excel in exams and assignments, and lay a strong foundation for lifelong learning. Researchers and Academics. Reading comprehension strategies are also important for researchers and academics who rely on critically analyzing written texts to advance knowledge in their respective fields. By employing effective comprehension strategies, researchers can synthesize information from multiple sources, evaluate the validity of research findings, and communicate their ideas clearly and persuasively through written publications.

5. References

- Abhishek, B., Jyothirmayi, M., Sirisha, K., & Thanishka, S. (2022). Text summarization based on ranking techniques. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Informatics (IC3I)*, 1463–1467. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IC3I56241.2022.10072962>
- Adler, M. A., & Fisher, C. W. (2001). Center for the improvement of early reading achievement: Early reading programs in high-poverty schools: A case study of beating the odds. *The Reading Teacher*, 54(6), 616–619.
- Amaglobeli, M. G. (2023). An application of scaffolding instruction in the reading course for elementary cfl learners. *Journal of Education and Educational Research*, 2(3), 5–8. <https://doi.org/10.54097/jeer.v2i3.7124>
- Andres, O., & Janine, M. (2022). Scaffolding strategy to enhance reading sub-skills among young-adult learners. *Green World Journal*, 22–22. <https://doi.org/10.53313/gwj52022>
- Antoniou, F., & Souvignier, E. (2007). Strategy instruction in reading comprehension: An intervention study for students with learning disabilities. *Learning Disabilities: A Contemporary Journal*, 5(1), 41–57. <http://search.proquest.com/docview/61934637?accountid=15099>
- Beck, I. L., & McKeown, M. G. (2007). Increasing young low-income children’s oral vocabulary repertoires through rich and focused instruction. *The Elementary School Journal*, 107, 251–271. <https://doi.org/10.1086/511706>
- Becker, C. S. (1992). *Living and relating: An introduction to phenomenology*. American Psychological Association.
- Benedetta, C., Chris, W., & Kathleen, R. (2022). Prediction as a basis for skilled reading: Insights from modern language models. *Royal Society Open Science*, 9(6). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.211837>
- Blair, T. R., Rupley, W. H., & Nichols, W. D. (2007). The effective teacher of reading: Considering the “what” and “how” of instruction. *Reading Teacher*, 60(5), 432–432.
- Brault, M. W. (2012). Americans with disabilities: 2010. <http://www.census.gov/prod/2012pubs/p70-131.pdf>
- Carter, R., & Nunan, D. (2001). *The cambridge guide to teaching english to speakers of other languages*.
- Célia, O., João, L., & Louise, S. (2019). Teachers’ academic training for literacy instruction. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 42(3), 315–334. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2019.1576627>
- Chatman, T. (2015). *Effective comprehension instructional strategies for improving the reading levels of students with learning disabilities* [Doctoral Dissertation]. <http://www.proquest.com>
- Chen, H. (2009). Online reading comprehension strategies among fifth- and sixth-grade general and special education students. *Educational Research Perspective*, 37, 79–109.
- Christine, M. (2011). Providing support to families with specific regard to the removal of barriers that exist for families trying to provide academic support at home.
- Clarke, P., Truelove, E., Hulme, C., & Snowling, M. (2013). *Developing reading comprehension*. Wiley.

- Cotter, J. (2012). *Understanding the relationship between reading fluency and reading comprehension: Fluency strategies as a focus for instruction* [Master's thesis, St. John Fisher College].
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approaches* (2nd). SAGE Publications.
- Cromley, J. G., & Azevedo, R. (2007). Testing and refining the direct and inferential mediation model of reading comprehension. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 99*(2), 311–325. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.99.2.311>
- Cunningham, A. E., & Stanovich, K. E. (1997). Early reading acquisition and its relation to reading experience and ability 10 years later. *Developmental Psychology, 33*(6), 934–945. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649.33.6.934>
- Douglas, F., & Nancy, F. (2018). Using questions to drive content area learning: Revising old favorites. *The Reading Teacher, 72*(3), 406–411. <https://doi.org/10.1002/TRTR.1741>
- Dung, D. T. X., & Thrang, T. T. T. (2022). Exploring the connection between teacher questioning and student learning behavior from a discourse perspective – a case study. *Ho Chi Minh City Open University Journal of Science – Social Sciences, 12*(2), 32–45. <https://doi.org/10.46223/hcmcoujs.soci.en.12.2.2583.2022>
- Effat, F., Teomara, R., & Collin, F. L. (2022). Predictive student modelling in an online reading platform. *AAAI Conference Proceedings, 36*(11), 12735–12743. <https://doi.org/10.1609/aaai.v36i11.21551>
- Elise, K. S., Thijs, M. J. N., & Maria, T. S.-d. J. (2022). Does feedback targeting text comprehension trigger the use of reading strategies or changes in readers' attitudes? a meta-analysis. *Journal of Research in Reading, 45*(2), 171–188. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9817.12389>
- Fletcher-Janzen, E., Reynolds, C. R., & Vannest, K. J. (2013). Reading comprehension. In *Encyclopedia of special education: A reference for the education of the handicapped and other exceptional children and adults*. Wiley.
- Ford, M. P., & Optiz, M. F. (2007). A national survey of guided reading practices: What we can learn from primary teachers. *Literary Research and Instruction, 47*, 309–337. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19388070802332895>
- for Economic Cooperation, O. (, & Development). (2008). *Teaching, learning and assessment for adults: Improving foundation skills*. OECD. <https://www.oecd.org/education/ceeri/teachinglearningandassessmentforadultsimprovingfoundationskills.ht>
- for Education Statistics, N. C. (2011). Reading performance [Education Department, Washington, D.C.: U.S.]. http://nces.ed.gov/programs/coe/pdf/coe_cnb.pdf
- Group, R. R. S. (2002). *Reading for understanding: Toward an r&d program in reading comprehension*. RAND. https://www.rand.org/pubs/monograph_reports/MR1465.html
- Hock, M., & Mellard, D. (2005). Reading comprehension strategies for adult literacy outcomes. In *Improving literacy instruction for adults*. National Institute of Child Health; Human Development, National Institute for Literacy, USDE Office of Vocational; Adult Education.
- Hoeh, E. (2015). *Mapping a path to understanding: Supporting the comprehension of narrative text for students with learning disabilities and typically developing peers* [Doctoral dissertation, ProQuest Dissertations and Theses] [pp. 77-83]. <http://www.proquest.com>

- Hollenbeck, A. (2011). Instructional makeover: Supporting the reading comprehension of students with learning disabilities in a discussion-based format. *Intervention in School and Clinic*, 46(4), 211–220. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1053451210389035>
- Ida, F. R., & Anik, N. W. (2013). Autonomous learning in reading class: Building the students' independent character. *Journal of Education*, 41(1).
- Isabella, H., & Aisyah, A. (2023). Pelatihan pengembangan kegiatan literasi kurikulum merdeka belajar merdeka bermain di tk aisyiah bustanul athfal 14 kecamatan karangpilang surabaya. *Devote*, 2(1), 35–38. <https://doi.org/10.55681/devote.v2i1.1085>
- Jane, C. (2021). Supporting preservice teachers to become informed teachers of reading through one-to-one tutoring in an english initial teacher education setting. *Education 3-13*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004279.2021.1985578>
- Jiménez-Fernández, G. (2015). Detective questions: A strategy for improving inference-making in children with mild disabilities. *Intervention in School and Clinic*, 51(1), 45–50. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1053451215577477>
- Kalof, L., & Dietz, T. (2008). *Essentials of social research*. McGraw-Hill Education.
- Lucy, R. S. (2022). *Creating positive, inclusive learning environments: Working with learners with additional and diverse needs*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009154048.013>
- Luh, R. N. (2022). Scaffolding technique in reading comprehension in the junior high school. *Journal of Educational Study*, 2(2), 142–150. <https://doi.org/10.36663/joes.v2i2.275>
- Luz, M. J. (2007). Literature and literacy: A nation of non-readers. <https://old.pcij.org/stories/a-nation-of-nonreaders/>
- Mahdavi, J. N., & Tensfeldt, L. (2013). Untangling reading comprehension strategy instruction: Assisting struggling readers in the primary grades. *Preventing School Failure*, 57(2), 77–92. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1045988X.2012.668576>
- Maria, R. R., & Jahaira, P. B. (2021). The effect of summarizing narrative texts to improve reading comprehension. *Forum Tadris*, 6(2), 94–110. <https://doi.org/10.18196/FTL.V6I2.11707>
- Marshall, P. (n.d.). The importance of reading comprehension [Retrieved from <http://www.k12reader.com/the-importance-of-reading-comprehension/>].
- Mason, L. H. (2004). Explicit self-regulated strategy development versus reciprocal questioning: Effects on reading comprehension among struggling readers. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 96(2), 283–296. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.96.2.283>
- Melissa, F. B., & Michele, J. (2021). How to discuss books with your kids (even when you haven't read them!) In *Routledge* (pp. 285–289). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003238287-47>
- Merga, M. K. (2022). Librarians creating environments for reading and wellbeing. <https://doi.org/10.29085/9781783305865.007>
- Mi-ea, L., & Gye, H. K. (2023). Augusto boal's theatre practice and reading education: Focused on the 'questioning' reading method. *The Korean Society of Culture and Convergence*, 45(3), 887–902. <https://doi.org/10.33645/cnc.2023.03.45.03.887>
- Millrood, R. P. (2001). *Modular course in elt methodology*.
- Mosenthal, P. B. (2000). Improving reading practice with reading theory: The procrustean approach. *Reading Teacher*, 40, 108–111.
- Moustakas, C. (1995). Phenomenological research method.

- Nguyen, M. T., & Nhu, V. Q. P. (2021). Using summarizing techniques to integrate writing into reading lessons for efl students. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 26(2), 89–96. <https://doi.org/10.52155/IJPSAT.V26.2.3079>
- of Education, D. (2013). Care for the non-readers program [Department of Education-Zamboanga del Sur Division].
- of Education, U. D. (2003). Identifying and implementing educational practices supported by rigorous evidence: A user friendly guide. <http://www.ed.gov/rschstat/research/pubs/rigorousetid/rigorousetid.pdf>
- Panel, N. R. (2000). *Teaching children to read: An evidence-based report*. National Institute of Child Health; Human Development.
- Paran, A. (2000). Reading in efl: Facts and fictions. *ELT Journal*, 50(1), 25–34.
- Pardo, L. S. (2004). What every teacher needs to know about reading comprehension. *The Reading Teacher*, 58(7), 272–280. <https://doi.org/10.1002/TRTR.01064>
- Pinto, I. (2009). *Children's plays and illustrations: Embodiment resources for reading practices*. Universidade Católica Portuguesa.
- Ramadani, R., Andrysyah, A., Siska, H., Asri, S., & D., E. (2022). Lecturers' feedback on students' reading at politeknik lp3i medan. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI) Journal*, 5(3). <https://doi.org/10.33258/birci.v5i3.6638>
- Reese, E., Sparks, A., & Leyva, D. (2010). A review of parent interventions for preschool children's language and emergent literacy. *Journal of Early Childhood Literacy*, 10, 97–117. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468798409356987>
- Rose, J. (2006). *Independent review of the teaching of early reading*. DfES.
- Ruiz, Y. (2015). *Improving reading comprehension through the use of interactive reading strategies: A quantitative study* [Doctoral dissertation, ProQuest Dissertations]. <http://www.proquest.com>
- Ryan, D. K., Joseph, P. M., Keith, K. M., Christopher, P. P., & Melissa, R. (2019). Understanding how language-specific and domain-general resources support comprehension. *Discourse Processes*, 56(7), 530–552. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0163853X.2018.1519358>
- Samuel, B., Matias, B., & Michele, G. (2022). Research insights: Does educational support for struggling students also benefit high achievers? *Education Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.18235/0004366>
- Sara, K. N., & Ramlee, M. (2017). Independent learning of english literature students: Learning from an iranian experience. *Geografia: Malaysian Journal of Society and Space*, 12(3).
- Sencibaugh, J. M. (2007). Meta-analysis of reading comprehension interventions for students with learning disabilities: Strategies and implications. *Reading Improvement*, 44(1), 6–22. <http://www.proquest.com>
- Sénéchal, M. (1997). The differential effect of storybook reading on preschoolers' acquisition of expressive and receptive vocabulary. *Journal of Child Language*, 24, 123–138. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0305000996003005>
- Shanahan, T. (2006). *Developing literacy in second-language learners: A report of the national literacy panel on minority-language children and youth*. Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Stobbe, M. (2001). *Surgeon general's warning: How politics crippled the nation's doctor*. University of California Press.

- Taylor, B. M., Pearson, P. D., Clark, K., & Warpole, S. (2000). Effective schools and accomplished teachers: Lessons about primary-grade reading instruction in low-income schools. *Elementary School Journal*, 101(2), 121–165. <http://www.journals.uchicago.edu/toc/esj/current>
- To Choose a Teaching Career?, S. (2001). Paper presented at the international educational research conference. *International Educational Research Conference*, 79–102.
- Tong, X., et al. (2011). Language deficits in poor comprehenders: A case for the simple view of reading. *J. Speech Lang. Hear. Res.*, 49, 278–293. [https://doi.org/10.1044/1092-4388\(2006/023\)](https://doi.org/10.1044/1092-4388(2006/023))
- Van der Velde, W., & Ernst, O. (2009). The future of ebooks? will print disappear? an end user perspective. *Library Hi Tech*, 27(4), 570–583.
- Vidyagouri, B. H., & BibiSadiqa, M. D. (2022). Text summarization using machine learning algorithm. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Computer Science, Engineering, and Information Technology*, 167–173. <https://doi.org/10.32628/cseit228421>
- Vukile, D. M. (2021). Advancing text prediction skills through translanguaging. *Reading and Writing*, 12(1), 10–. <https://doi.org/10.4102/RW.V12I1.284>
- Willis, J. (2009). What the brain suggests for teaching reading strategies. *Educational Reform*, 73(4), 333–346.
- Wolley, G. (2008). The assessment of reading comprehension difficulties for reading intervention. *Australian Journal of Learning Difficulties*, 13(1), 51–62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19404150802093729>
- Wolley, G. (2011). *Reading comprehension: Assisting children with learning difficulties*. Springer.
- Wong, B. (2011). *Learning about learning disabilities*. Elsevier Science. <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/wmichlib-ebooks/detail.action?docID=294624>
- Xiaomei, S. (2022). Scaffolded extensive reading: A concept drawn from two efl reading programmes. *Language Teaching Research*, 136216882211412–136216882211412. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13621688221141297>
- Xu, Z. (2023). Research on questioning strategies to improve students' thinking quality in english reading teaching in senior high school. *Frontiers in Sustainable Development*, 3(4), 79–82. <https://doi.org/10.54691/fsd.v3i4.4765>
- Yang, D. (2021). A research on the influence of scaffolding teaching on junior high school students' english reading ability. *World Journal of English Language*, 11(2), 43–. <https://doi.org/10.5430/WJEL.V11N2P43>
- Yin, R. K. (2003). *Case study research: Design and methods (3rd ed.)* Sage.
- Yu, B., Ferdy, H., Catia, C., Roeland, V. H., & Helmer, S. (2022). The effects of implicit and explicit feedback in an asr-based reading tutor for dutch first-graders. *Interspeech 2022*, 4476–4480. <https://doi.org/10.21437/interspeech.2022-10810>